

Customer Satisfaction Among Online Shoppers: A Study of Business Administration Students

Denmark S. Ruiz¹; Reshyl Gabat-Lopez, MMBM^{2*}; Carolyn M. Jayo³; Jhona C. Cagol⁴; Melchie A. Apura⁵
Armando C. Caparida⁶; Mariafe M. Caparida⁷; Yonalyn A. Espero⁸
Philippine College Foundation
Valencia City, Bukidnon

Corresponding Author:- Reshyl Gabat-Lopez, MMBM^{2*}

Abstract:- This study aimed to evaluate the satisfaction level of respondents regarding online shopping, specifically conducted at the Philippine College Foundation in Valencia City, Bukidnon over two weeks in October 2023. The survey gathered responses from 157 Bachelor of Science in Business Administration students enrolled in the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year, all of whom had experience with online shopping. Descriptive statistics including frequency, mean, and standard deviation were utilized by the researchers to address the study's objectives. The data collection involved a self-designed questionnaire crafted to comprehensively capture the essential facets of the study. The findings revealed a prevalent satisfaction among respondents in various aspects of online shopping, notably in terms of convenience, product delivery, and product quality, which significantly influenced overall customer satisfaction within the online shopping context. This indicates a strong inclination among respondents towards favoring online shopping as a preferred method for making purchases.

Keywords:- Customer Satisfaction, Online Shopping.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world of commerce has witnessed extensive digital transformation, and one of the sectors most significantly impacted by this change is online purchasing. In recent years, online shopping has experienced explosive growth, firmly establishing itself as a quick and convenient means for consumers to purchase. This transformation is particularly significant for students on top of this digital shift. Students are now enthusiastic online shoppers, drawn to the convenience of accessing a wide array of products at competitive prices and the freedom to shop at their convenience.

Being digital groups, students eagerly embrace technology, engaging in various online activities, including purchasing products and services. Understanding their online shopping behavior and assessing their satisfaction with this mode of commerce is crucial for entrepreneurs, educators, and regulators.

Today, internet shopping has become a straightforward process for acquiring everyday goods due to the widespread use of smartphones, computers, and tablets. Online shopping leads to electronic commerce, driving customers' decisions to purchase products from specific organizations (Souca, 2014). The Philippines, in particular, has seen an upward trend in demand for e-commerce, with the rise of smartphones and desktop computers leading to an increase in online purchases among Filipinos. The advancement of technology has reshaped people's daily lives, with the Internet playing a vital role in this transformation. As a result, the traditional shopping mode in physical stores has evolved into a more efficient and popular system known as e-commerce Rudansky-loppers (2014).

According to data from January 2021, the Philippines had 73.91 million internet users, which increased by 4.2 million between 2020 and 2021. The United States had 79.9 million social media users, while the Philippines boasted 89.00 million (Bureau of Statistics). This significant rise in social media users has made platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube more accessible, transforming them into avenues for online shopping and connecting sellers and retailers with their customers (Singh & Singh, 2018). Online shopping has emerged as a lifeline for busy individuals juggling various priorities. With items delivered to their doorstep, it offers a convenient solution for meeting shopping needs. However, it has challenges, as customers can experience satisfaction and dissatisfaction with their purchases. Product defects and incorrect deliveries can mar the online shopping experience (Karthikeyan, 2016).

Online privacy and security concerns are prevalent in online shopping, especially in developing countries where comprehensive regulations may be lacking. Reports of internet fraud deter customers from engaging in online purchases. Therefore, a comprehensive examination of customer satisfaction, including pre-purchase and post-purchase behavior, is essential to alleviate these concerns (Akram, 2018).

This study seeks to provide valuable insights for e-commerce companies, academic institutions, and policymakers. Analyzing the factors influencing student satisfaction in online shopping aims to enhance the online shopping experience and foster lasting customer relationships. This study contributes to the body of knowledge concerning students' satisfaction with online purchasing by offering insight into their experiences and levels of satisfaction.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive-quantitative research design. The descriptive quantitative research design aims to gather and analyze data to describe or quantify a particular phenomenon or population. It involves collecting data through structured surveys, questionnaires, or observations and then analyzing it using statistical techniques to draw meaningful conclusions (Creswell, 2013). This research design allows researchers to measure variables, identify patterns, and make predictions. It focuses on collecting numerical data and using statistical analysis to describe the studied topic (Babbie, 2016) comprehensively.

Furthermore, this research was conducted at the Philippine College Foundation, an appropriate locale for this study. Philippine College Foundation (PCF) is a nonstock, nonprofit private school offering courses, including the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration. The decision of the researchers to select the school as the study's locale is based on the availability of a suitable sample population of online shoppers among the students. Conducting the research at the school allows easy access to the participants, facilitating data collection and analysis.

Respondents are only one hundred (100) second-year bonafide students of the Philippine College Foundation who were enrolled during the second semester of the school year 2022-2023 and are enrolled as third-year students of the school year 2023-2024 and actively engage in online shopping. These students are an excellent sample for investigating customer satisfaction in an online purchasing setting since they are often avid buyers and represent a diverse group with varying online shopping experiences.

This study employed a stratified sampling technique to allow researchers to gain a more reliable and precise measure of population characteristics, particularly when the population is varied and divided into subgroups with considerably distinct features. As cited by the study of Ayoub, H., & Twesige, D. (2022), stratified sampling is a probability sampling method used in sample surveys; the target population elements are divided into distinct groups or strata, and the elements within each stratum are similar to each other in terms of select characteristics of importance to the research (Parsons, 2017).

The researchers derived a sample size of 157 out of the total population of 262 second-year BSBA students in PCF. The sample distribution was computed proportionately by dividing the total sample by the total population multiplied

by the population per number of students. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents by section.

To collect data for the study, the researchers developed a self-made questionnaire. Furthermore, the questionnaire is divided into two parts. The first section focuses on the demographic profile of students, which includes age, gender, marital status, and monthly allowance. The second section assessed customer satisfaction with online shopping in terms of Convenience (10 indicators), product delivery (5 indicators), and product quality (10 indicators), for a total of 25 indicators rated on a 5-point Likert scale of 5 (Highly Satisfied), 4 (Satisfied), 3 (Moderately Satisfied), 2 (Less Satisfied), and 1 (Unsatisfied). This questionnaire was designed to measure respondents' level of satisfaction when shopping online.

Finally, statistical tools including frequency counts were used to determine the demographic profiles of the respondents, weighted mean to assess the level of customer satisfaction with online purchasing, and standard deviation for evaluating data dispersion. In statistics, a frequency distribution conveys how often a particular entry appears in the dataset (Merbitz et al. (2016). This study employed frequency distribution to categorize respondents by age, gender, marital status, and monthly allowance. The mean signifies the ratio of the sum of observations to the number of comments, as defined by Panneerslvam (2008). In this research, researchers utilized this statistical method to calculate the average score for each indicator, as rated by the respondents.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result revealed that among the 157 respondents engaging in online shopping, over half of the respondents fall within the 19-24 age bracket, representing 54.1% of the total. This indicates that this group has a strong tendency for online purchasing and is highly active in this activity. This is consistent with earlier studies conducted by Shanthi & Kanniah (2015), which showed that people in the 20–25 age range like to shop online while those in the older age groups are less likely to do so. Conversely, findings from Kanchan, Kumar, and Gupta's (2015) study revealed that individuals aged 30-45 exhibit more significant interest in online shopping, presenting a contrast to the primary trend observed in this study.

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile	f	%
Age		
19-24	85	54.1
25-30	28	17.8
31-36	26	16.8
37 above	18	11.5
Total	157	100
Sex		
Male	34	21.7
Female	123	78.3
Total	157	100
Marital status		
Single	116	73.9
Married	41	26.1
Total	157	100
Monthly Allowance		
1000-2000	100	63.7
2001-3000	25	15.9
3001-4000	12	7.6
4001-5000	9	5.7
5001 above	11	7.0
Total	157	100

As to sex, the data revealed that out of 157 respondents, 78.3% are female, and 21.7% are male. This implies that females are more active online shoppers than males. In the case of PCF students, most of them are female, which makes them more prone to online shopping since they purchase things like personal care and fashion items, unlike males, who are smaller in number. According to Bancoro (2023), females are far more likely than males to shop online. In contrast, the intention to shop online is higher among men than it is among women (Bhat et al. (2021).

Regarding marital status, the data indicates that 73.9% of respondents are single, while 26.1% are married. This highlights a notable inclination of unmarried individuals towards online shopping, corroborating findings from Singh and Kashyap (2015) study and Bhat et al. (2021), which similarly emphasized the preference for online shopping among unmarried consumers. However, Shalini and Malini's (2015) study presents a contrasting perspective, suggesting that married consumers exhibit a higher preference for internet shopping compared to single consumers.

Examining the monthly allowance distribution among respondents, a significant portion (63.7%) falls within the 1,000-2,000 range despite being a relatively modest income bracket. This reflects the willingness of respondents, particularly PCF students, to allocate a portion of their limited income toward online purchases. This behavior aligns with Sharma and Parmar, (2018) study, which observed that customers with intermediate to higher incomes tend to shop online more frequently than those with lower incomes. Additionally, Mehrotra et al. (2019) further support this trend, indicating a greater propensity for online shopping among individuals with higher earnings.

Table 2 Level of Customer Satisfaction Towards Online Shopping in Terms of Convenience

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualifying Statement
1. I find online shopping accessible.	4.07	0.86	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
2. I find online shopping transaction easy and hassle-free.	4.08	0.86	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
3. I find online shopping provide detailed prices on items offered.	3.96	0.89	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
4. I find online shopping product information in clear and concise manner.	3.66	0.78	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
5. I find online shopping a simple ordering process.	4.15	0.79	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
6. I find the checkout process for online shopping good and efficient.	3.94	0.84	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
7. I used to do online shopping because of its open-time ordering process.	4.10	0.81	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
8. I used to do online shopping because of its simplicity of discovering deals or discounts in different shops.	4.04	0.80	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
9. I used to purchase online because it was so simple to check on the progress of my order.	4.05	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
10. I used to buy products online since it gives me a variety of brand choices.	3.80	0.92	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
OVERALL MEAN	3.96	0.84	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
Legend	4.21-5.00	Highly Satisfied	Online shopping is extremely favorable	
	3.41-4.20	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable	
	2.61-3.40	Moderately Satisfied	Online shopping is somewhat favorable	
	1.81-2.60	Less Satisfied	Online shopping is slightly favorable	
	1.00-1.80	Unsatisfied	Online shopping is not favorable	

Table 2 highlights the top three mean indicators among respondents: "I find online shopping's ordering process simple" (4.15), "I used to do online shopping due to its open-time ordering process" (4.10), and "I and online shopping transactions easy and hassle-free" (4.08). This implies that PCF students exhibit a strong affinity for online shopping due to its inherent conveniences: the ability to browse and purchase at any time, the convenience of shopping from their homes, simplified online transactions, and access to a diverse range of products from various brands and sellers. This extensive array of options provides students with a wide selection to choose from, contributing to their enjoyment of the online shopping experience. Thus, it means that online shopping is very favorable to students in making purchase.

Research by Kaura et al. (2015) emphasizes that offering Convenience, whether through streamlined online transactions or by expanding payment options, significantly enhances customer satisfaction. When users perceive the online ordering process as easy and user-friendly, they consider the system useful (Abdullah et al. 2017). Moreover, customers are inclined to make online purchases when they find the shopping platform easy to navigate and use (Mpfu et al. 2019).

However the convenience and efficiency of online checkout processes, the overall satisfaction of students lessens if the product information is not presented clearly, hindering their ability to confidently make purchase

decisions as well as recommendation to their relatives and friends. This finding is supported by the study of Jiang, Yang, and Jun (2013), which claimed that Convenience has a favorable impact on general consumer satisfaction. According to Prasetyo and Fuente (2020), happy customers are more likely to stick with the retailer, use them more frequently, refer them to others, and have a better overall experience. Customer happiness can be influenced by a variety of factors, including the ability to choose from a variety of items Mahmud, Imtiaz, Ahmed (2019).

Table 3 Level of Customer Satisfaction Towards Online Shopping in Terms of Delivery of Product

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Online shopping guaranteed on time delivery of purchased products.	3.71	0.88	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
2. Online shopping offers good condition items.	3.48	0.92	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
3. Online shopping provides excellent service.	3.61	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
4. Online purchasing offers flexible delivery option.	3.80	0.80	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
5. Online shopping allows customers to track or check purchased product accurately.	3.94	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
OVERALL MEAN	3.71	0.86	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
Legend:				
4.21-5.00	Highly Satisfied	Online shopping is extremely favorable		
3.41-4.20	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable		
2.61-3.40	Moderately Satisfied	Online shopping is somewhat favorable		
1.81-2.60	Less Satisfied	Online shopping is slightly favorable		
1.00-1.80	Unsatisfied	Online shopping is not favorable		

Table 3 reveals that among the five indicators, the statement "Online shopping allows customers to accurately track or check purchased products" received the highest rating, achieving a mean of 3.94 or a verbal description of "satisfied." For PCF students, this aspect of online shopping is very favorable to them as it gives a smooth and convenient purchasing process. The ability to monitor purchased products holds significant value, primarily when items are intended for special events or occasions. Customers often seek assurance regarding the delivery timeline, whether it aligns with their expectations or potentially arrives earlier.

Additionally, Cao et al. (2018) found that tracking mechanisms involving multichannel methods like email or text alerts for delivery updates could predict customer satisfaction among online shoppers in China and Taiwan. Moreover, recent studies have emphasized the impact of efficient delivery on customer satisfaction. Chou et al. (2015) research highlighted the influence of promised delivery times on customer satisfaction. As evidenced by

Mofokeng (2021), South African researchers emphasized the significance of timely product deliveries in enhancing online customers' satisfaction levels.

Meanwhile, among the indicators, "Online shopping offers items in good condition" received the lowest mean score of 3.48. This outcome suggests that respondents rated this aspect the lowest, possibly due to concerns regarding the condition of delivered products. Students might encounter challenges such as delays, mishandling of parcels, or unforeseen circumstances while transporting purchased items. In developed countries, dissatisfaction among online shoppers often stems from businesses' failure to provide expedited or timely deliveries, as highlighted in Capgemini (2019). Moreover, instances of online stores delivering products entirely different from what the customer ordered or, worse, delivering empty packages, as noted by Al-Jahwari et al. (2018), contribute to customer discontentment and impact the perceived reliability of online shopping platforms.

Table 4 Level of Customer Satisfaction Towards Online Shopping in Terms of Product Quality

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualifying Statement
1. I used to shop online because they offer accurate products.	3.56	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
2. I used to purchase products via online because it provides quality of materials.	3.36	0.87	Moderately Satisfied	Online shopping is somewhat favorable
3. I used to do online shopping because of the packaging quality.	3.50	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
4. I used to do online shopping because of its defect free products.	3.50	0.94	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
5. I find the products/items in online shops durable.	3.36	0.85	Moderately Satisfied	Online shopping is somewhat favorable
6. I find the features and function of products in online shops easy to access.	3.76	0.75	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
7. I used to buy products online because of high-quality labeling.	3.34	0.82	Moderately Satisfied	Online shopping is somewhat favorable
8. I used to do online shopping because of its accurate and detailed information about the products.	3.47	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
9. I used to purchase online due to the availability of products and selection of trusted brands.	3.63	0.83	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
10. I find online products with unique designs.	3.85	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
OVERALL MEAN	3.49	0.85	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable
Legend:				
4.21-5.00	Highly Satisfied	Online shopping is extremely favorable		
3.41-4.20	Satisfied	Online shopping is very favorable		
2.61-3.40	Moderately Satisfied	Online shopping is somewhat favorable		
1.81-2.60	Less Satisfied	Online shopping is slightly favorable		
1.00-1.80	Unsatisfied	Online shopping is not favorable		

These results signify PCF students' satisfaction with the quality of products offered through online shopping platforms. Students demonstrate contentment with the product quality as they make informed choices by considering various factors such as the product source, customer reviews, return policies, product descriptions, pricing, and brand reputation. This practice leads them to purchase from reliable and trustworthy online retailers. Research by Vasi et al. (2019) emphasizes that customer satisfaction in online purchases is notably influenced by the overall product quality, superiority, and performance. This reflects the idea that perceived quality and customer satisfaction arise when consumer perceptions of online services surpass their expectations. Similarly, Makudza (2021) further supports this notion, highlighting that exceeding consumer expectations improves quality perception and subsequent satisfaction.

Online shoppers face limitations as they cannot physically inspect items before purchasing, leading to concerns about durability, authenticity, or materials used in the products. To prevent dissatisfying customers, sellers should transparently present product features online before listing them for sale. The presence of complete product information on a website plays a crucial role in assisting consumers to make well-informed purchasing decisions when shopping online (Sam & Sharma, 2015). According to Bhatti et al. (2018), inadequate product quality information online stands as a factor that may deter customers from continuing to purchase through online platforms. Additionally, Shumba and Ferreira (2023) assert that service providers must offer honest product descriptions to allow customers to accurately assess their quality expectations when purchasing goods online.

Overall result shows that regarding satisfaction, the high ratings for Convenience, Delivery, and product quality among PCF students affirm the importance they place on the ease and accessibility offered by online shopping. Despite challenges like product information clarity and checkout efficiency, the overall positive feeling emphasizes the significance of Convenience and diverse product choices. Moreover, the appreciation for unique product designs and the availability of trusted brands further enrich their satisfaction with the online shopping experience.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdallah, N. (2021). Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353194157> dated, May 10, 2023
- [2]. Abdullah, D., Jayaraman, K., Shariff, D. N., Bahari, K. A., dan Nor, N. M. (2017). The effects of perceived interactivity, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness on online hotel booking intention: A conceptual framework. *International Academic Research Journal of Social Science*, 3(1), 16-23.
- [3]. Abdullah, D., Jayaraman, K., Shariff, D. N., Bahari, K. A., dan Nor, N. M. (2017). The effects of perceived interactivity, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness on online hotel booking intention: A conceptual framework. *International Academic Research Journal of Social Science*, 3(1), 16-23.
- [4]. Afzal, S., Chandio, A. K., Shaikh, S., Bhand, M., and Ghumro, B. A. (2013). Factors behind brand switching in cellular networks. *Int. J. Asian Soc. Science* 3, 299–307.
- [5]. Agung W. A., N. (2018). The Impact of Interpersonal Communication toward Customer Satisfaction: The Case of Customer Service of Sari Asih Hospital. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 150, 05087. doi:10.1051/mateconf/201815005087 10.1051/mateconf/201815005087
- [6]. Akram, U., Hui, P., Kaleem Khan, M., Tanveer, Y., Mehmood, K., & Ahmad, W. (2018). How website quality affects online impulse buying: Moderating effects of sales promotion and credit card use. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 30(1), 235-256.
- [7]. Akroush, M.N. and Al-Debei, M.M. (2015). An integrated model of factors affecting consumer attitudes towards online shopping. 21, 1353–1376.
- [8]. Al Karim, R. (2013). Customer Satisfaction in Online Shopping: a study into the reasons for motivations and inhibitions. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 11(6), 13-20.
- [9]. Al-Jahwari, N. S., Khan, M. F. R., Al Kalbani, G. K., & Al Khansouri, S. S. (2018). Factors influencing customer satisfaction of online shopping in Oman – Youth perspective. *Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews*, 6(2), 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2018.628>
- [10]. Amanah, D. (2018). Kepuasan Pengunjung Tempat Wisata Pemandian Hairis Waterpark Medan. *Jurnal Plans*, (May).
- [11]. Amoah, F. and Marriott, A. (2021). Dimensions of online shopping experience and satisfaction: An application of Pine and Gilmore's 4Es. *African Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 16(1), pp. 117-137.
- [12]. Aslam, W., Arif, I., Farhat, K., and Khursheed, M. (2018). The role of customer trust, service quality and value dimensions in determining satisfaction and loyalty: an Empirical study of mobile telecommunication industry in Pakistan. *Market-Tržište* 30, 177–194. doi: 10.22598/mt/2018.30.2.177
- [13]. Ayeni, A., 2014. Empirics of Standard Deviation. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1444.6729>
- [14]. Ayoub, H., & Twesige, D. (2022). Influence of Internal Business Environment on the Growth of Microfinance Institutions in Rwanda (Case Study Musanze District). <https://doi.org/10.22158/jetr.v4n1p23>

- [15]. Babbie, E. (2016). *The Practice of Social Research* (14th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- [16]. Bachrach, D. G., Ogilvie, J., Rapp, A. and Calamusa IV, J. (2016). *More than a showroom: Strategies for winning back on-line shoppers*, 1st edition, Palgrave MacMillian, US.
- [17]. Balderaz & Campos, (2020). The Influence of Customer-Based Brand Equity on Online Shopping Satisfaction among Public Teachers in Davao Del Sur, Philippines
- [18]. Balderaz, G, B, B., & Campos, K, P. (2020). The influence of customer-based brand equity on online shopping satisfaction among public teachers in Davao Del Sur, Philippines. *Review of integrative Business and economics Research*, 9(2).
- [19]. Bancoro, J., (2023). Empirical analysis on the preferences of Negros Oriental State University students to online shopping. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2 (4), 1387-1398. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370590358_Empirical_Analysis_on_the_Preference_of_Negros_Oriental_State_University_Students_to_Online_Shopping
- [20]. Bashir, R., Mehboob, I., & Bhatti, W. K. (2015). Effects of online shopping trends on consumer buying Behavior: an empirical study of Pakistan, *Journal of Management and Research*, 2(2), 1-25.
- [21]. Bhat, S., Islam, S., and Sheikh, A. (2021). Evaluating the influence of consumer demographics on online purchase intention: An E-tail Perspective. *Paradigm* 25 (5), 141-160. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/09718907211045185>
- [22]. Bhatti, A., Saad, S., and Gbadebo, S. M., (2018). Convenience risk, product risk, and perceived risk influence on online shopping: Moderating effect of attitude. *International Journal of Business Management*, 3(2), pp. 1-11.
- [23]. Blandina, S. Jiří, P., (2019). Gender differences and wellbeing values in adolescent online shopping. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management* [online]., vol. 47, iss. 6, s. 623-642. [cit. 2023-05-26]. ISSN 0959-0552. Dostupné z: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJRDM-08-2017-0173/full/html>.
- [24]. Bojang, I., Medvedev, M. A., Spasov, K. B., & Matvevnina, A. I. (2017, December). Determinants of trust in B2C e-commerce and their relationship with consumer online trust. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 1910, No. 1, p. 020001). AIP Publishing.
- [25]. Bradić, M., Kosar, L., & Kalenjuk, B. (2013). Business guests satisfaction in the hotel industry: A case study of North American hotel chains. *Turizam*, 17(2), 60-70.
- [26]. Bruschi, I., Schwarz, B., & Schmitt, R. (2019). David versus Goliath – Service quality factors for niche providers in online retailing. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 50, 266–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.05.008>
- [27]. Bureau of Statistics (2021). Internet users in the Philippines. Retrieved April 31, 2023, from <https://datareportal/reports/digital-2021-philippines>
- [28]. Butt, M. M., Rose, S., Wilkins, S., and Haq, J. U. (2017). MNCs and religious influences in global markets: drivers of consumer-based halal brand equity. *Int. Market. Rev.* 12:277. doi: 10.1108/IMR-12-2015-0277
- [29]. Campo, K., and Breugelmans, E. (2015). Buying Groceries in Brick and Click Stores: Category Allocation Decisions and the Moderating Effect of Online Buying Experience. *J. Interact. Mark.* 31, 63–78
- [30]. Cao, Y., Ajjan, H., & Hong, P. (2018). Post-purchase shipping and customer service experiences in online shopping and their impact on customer satisfaction: An empirical study with comparison. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 30(2), 400-416. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323323579_Post-purchase_shipping_and_customer_service_experiences_in_online_shopping_and_their_impact_on_customer_satisfaction_An_empirical_study_with_comparison
- [31]. Capgemini,(2019), The last-mile delivery challenge: Giving retail and consumer product customers a superior delivery experience without impacting profitability, viewed 07 March 2020, from <https://www.capgemini.com/wpcontent/uploads/2019/01/Report-Digital-%E2%80%9393-Last-Mile-DeliveryChallenge1.pdf>
- [32]. Cevher, E. (2014). İnternette Girişimciliğin Yeni Boyutu: Alışveriş Kulüpleri Siteleri ve Bu Siteler Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *Manas Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 3(3), 47-60.
- [33]. Chaing and Dholakia (2014). Factor Driving Consumer Intention to Shop Online: An Empirical Investigation: *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 13 (1&2), 177-183.
- [34]. Chandra. A. K., & Shiha, D. K. (2013). Factors affecting the online shopping behavior: a study with reference to Bhilai Drug. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Science*, 2(5), 160-177.
- [35]. Chang, S. H., Chih, W. H., Liou, D. K., & Yang, Y. T. (2016). The mediation of cognitive attitude for online shopping. *Information Technology & People*, 29, 618–646.10.1108/ITP-08-2014-0172.
- [36]. Chen, L. D., & Shen, X. L. (2015). Determinants of online group buying intention and satisfaction: A study on gender differences. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 51, 69-76.
- [37]. Chen, Y., & Dubinsky, A. J. (2013). A conceptual model of perceived customer value in e-commerce: A preliminary investigation. *Psychology & Marketing*, 30(3), 199-212.

- [38]. Chen, Y., Yan, X., Fan, W., & Gordon, M. (2015). Computers in Human Behavior The joint moderating role of trust propensity and gender on consumers' online shopping behavior. *computers in human behavior*, 43, 272–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.10.020> dated May 10, 2023
- [39]. Chitungo, S.K. and Munongo, S. (2013) 'Extending the technology acceptance model to mobile banking adoption in rural Zimbabwe', *Journal of Business Administration and Education*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp.51–79.
- [40]. Cho, Y., Im, I., Hiltz, S.R., & Fjermestad, J. (2016). The effects of post-purchase evaluation factors on online repurchase intention: A *privacy calculus perspective*. *Information Systems Journal*, 26(6), 567-599.
- [41]. Chou, S., Chen, C., & Lin, J. (2015). Female online shoppers: Examining the mediating roles of e-satisfaction and e-trust on e-loyalty development. *Internet Research*, 25(4), 542–561. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-01-2014-0006>
- [42]. Chowdhury, E., & Chowdhury, R. (2017). Online shopping in Bangladesh: A study on the motivational factors for e-commerce that influence shopper's affirmative tendency towards online shopping. *South Asian Journal of Marketing & Management Research*, 7(4), 20. doi: 10.5958/2249-877x.2017.00019.4
- [43]. Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- [44]. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Sage Publications.
- [45]. Dabija, D. C., Babut, R., Dinu, V., & Lugoian, M. I. (2017). Cross-generational analysis of information searching based on social media in Romania. *Transformations in Business and Economics*, 16(2).
- [46]. Dai, W., Arnulf, J. K., Iao, L., Wan, P., & Dai, H. (2019). Like or want? Gender differences in attitudes toward online shopping in China. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(4), 354-362.
- [47]. Datta, A., & Acharjee, M. (2018). Consumers attitude towards online shopping: Factors influencing young consumers to shop online in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 3(4), 01. doi: 10.18843/ijms/v5i3(4)/01
- [48]. Dawid, W., & Pokonieczny, K. (2023). Generalization of digital elevation models for military passability maps development. *Advances in Cartography and GIScience of the ICA*, 4, 6.
- [49]. Deyalage, P. A., and Kulathunga, D., 2020. Exploring key factors for customer satisfaction in online shopping: A systematic literature review. *International Business Management*, 6(1), pp. 163-190. <http://dr.lib.sjp.ac.lk/handle/123456789/10474>.
- [50]. Djumarno, S. A., and Said, D, (2018), "Effect of Product Quality and Price on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction", *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*.
- [51]. Duarte, P., Silva, S. C., & Ferreira, M. B. (2018). How convenient is it? Delivering online shopping convenience to enhance. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 44, 161-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.06.007>
- [52]. Dynamics, M., Volume, K. E., Books, T., Ludin, I. H. Bt, H and Cheng, B. L., (2014). "Factors influencing factors influencing customer satisfaction and e-loyalty: online shopping environment among the young adults," *Manag. Dyn. Knowl. Econ.*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 462–471
- [53]. Ezer, E. E., Darmadi, K., & Mulia, A. (2023, October). Enhancing reliability of consolidation design parameters for residual settlement estimation: a sensitivity analysis approach for existing container yard in Belawan, Medan. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1249, No. 1, p. 012038). IOP Publishing.
- [54]. Falk, T., Kunz, W.H., Schepers, J. and Mrozek, A.J. (2016), "How mobile payment influences the overall store price image", *Journal of Business Research*, 69(7), 2417-2423
- [55]. Flavián, C., & Guinalú, M. (2016). Consumer trust, perceived security and privacy policy: three basic elements of loyalty to a web site, *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 106(5), 601-620.
- [56]. Ganapathi, R. (2015). A study on factors affecting online shopping behavior of consumers in Chennai, *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, 2(2), 123-126.
- [57]. Ganesh, S. (2020). A Study on Consumer's Satisfaction Towards Online Shopping in Coimbatore City. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)* vol: 5.
- [58]. Ghoumrassi, Amine & Tigu, Gabriela. (2017). The impact of logistics management in customer satisfaction. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*. 11. 10.1515/picbe2017-0031.
- [59]. Giese, J. L., Giese, J. L., & Cote, J. A. (2016). Defining consumer satisfaction. *Academy of Marketing Science Review*, 1(1), 15. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joan_Giese/publication/235357014_Defining_Consumer_Satisfaction/links/5419a5790cf203f155ae0afb/Defining-Consumer-Satisfaction.pdf on 21/8/2019
- [60]. Gong, W.; Stump, R. L.; Maddox, L. M. (2013). Factors influencing consumers' online shopping in China. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 7(3), 214–230. Retrieved July 13, 2023, from <https://doi.org/doi:10.1108/JABS-02-2013-0006>
- [61]. Guido, G. (2015, January). Customer satisfaction. *ResearchGate*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313966638_Customer-Satisfaction dated September 25, 2023
- [62]. Gurung, R. A. R., & Prakash, G. (2018). An empirical investigation of trust, perceived value, and satisfaction in online shopping. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 41, 242-254.

- [63]. Ha, H. Y., & Janda, S. (2014). The effect of customized information on online purchase intentions. *Internet Research*, 24, 496–519. [10.1108/IntR-06-2013-0107](https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-06-2013-0107).
- [64]. Hair, J., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) (2nd edition)*. Los Angeles:
- [65]. Hague, P & Hague, N. (2016). *Customer satisfaction survey: The customer experience through the customer's eyes*. London: Cogent Publication
- [66]. Handoko, L. P. (2016). the Effect of Product Quality and Delivery Service on Online Customer Satisfaction in Zalora Indonesia. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*, 4(1), 1189–1199. <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v4i1.11876>
- [67]. Harvanko, A., Lust, K., Odlaug, B. L., Schreiber, L. R., Derbyshire, K., Christenson, G., & Grant, J. E. (2013). Prevalence and characteristics of compulsive buying in college students. *Psychiatry Research*, 210(3), 1079–1085. Retrieved July 13, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2013.08.048>
- [68]. Herviana, V, P, S. & Anik, L. A., (2018). “Pengaruh Kualitas Produk Dan Harga Terhadap Loyalitas Dengan Kepuasan Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Effect of Product Quality and Price on Loyalty with Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable)”, *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 6(1).
- [69]. Hong, Wei & Zheng, Changyuan & Wu, Linhai & Pu, Xujin. (2019). Analyzing the Relationship between Consumer Satisfaction and Fresh E-Commerce Logistics Service Using Text Mining Techniques. *Sustainability*. 11. 3570. [10.3390/su11133570](https://doi.org/10.3390/su11133570).
- [70]. Hooda, S. and Singh, N., 2018. Online apparel shopping. *Man-Made Textiles in India*, 46(3).
- [71]. Hou, J., & Elliott, K. (2016). Electronic Commerce Research and Applications Gender differences in online auctions. *ELECTRONIC COMMERCE RESEARCH AND APPLICATIONS*, 17, 123– 133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2016.04.004> dated May 10, 2023
- [72]. Hridhya V.V. (2021). A study on customer satisfaction towards online shopping: UNIVERSITY OF CALICUT
- [73]. Hsu, C. L., Lin, J. C. C., dan Chiang, H. S. (2013). The effects of blogger recommendations on customers' online shopping intentions. *Internet Research*, 23(1), 69- 88.
- [74]. Hsu, M. H., Chang, C. M., & Chuang, L. W. (2015). Understanding the determinants of online repeat purchase intention and moderating role of habit: The case of online group-buying in Taiwan. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(1), 45–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2014.09.002> on 7/2/2019
- [75]. Huang, W.-H.; Shen, G.C.; Liang, C.-L. (2019). The effect of threshold free shipping policies on online shoppers' willingness to pay for shipping. *J. Retail. Consum. Serv.* 48, 105–112.
- [76]. Hult, G. T. M., Sharma, P. N., Morgeson, F. V., III, & Zhang, Y. (2019). Antecedents and consequences of customer satisfaction: Do they differ across online
- [77]. IBOJO, B. O. (2015). Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Retention: A Case Study of a Reputable Bank in Oyo, Oyo State. Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*, 3(2), 42–53. Retrieved from www.arcjournals.org
- [78]. Irantaj, G., & Huseynov, F. (2018). Factors influencing customer satisfaction level in an e-commerce platform: A case study analysis of Digikala in Iran. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science*, 4(6), 19–27. Retrieved from <https://acikerisim.aydin.edu.tr/bitstream/11547/2312/1/502087.pdf> on 21/8/2019
- [79]. Jiang, L. A., Yang, Z., & Jun, M. (2013). Measuring consumer perceptions of online shopping convenience. *Journal of Service management*, 24(2), 191-214.
- [80]. Jiang, L., Yang, Z., & Jun, M. (2013). Measuring consumer perceptions of online Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research, Vol. 9, Supplementary Issue 2 356 Copyright © 2020 GMP Press and Printing shopping convenience. *Journal of Service Management*, 24(2), 191-214.
- [81]. Kamarulzaman, Y., Md. Yusof, R., & Abdullah, N. A. (2016). The impact of perceived value on online customer satisfaction and loyalty. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, 341-347.
- [82]. Kanchan. U., Kumar. N., and Gupta, A. (2015). A study of online purchase behaviour of customers in India. *ICTACT Journal on Management Studies*. 1 (3), 136-142. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/306382997_A_STUDY_OF_ONLINE_PURCHASE_BEHAVIOR_OF_CUSTOMERS_IN_INDIA
- [83]. Kannaiah. D., Shanti. R. (2015). The impact of augmented reality on e-commerce. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*. 8,64-73. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.academia.edu/83452800/The_Impact_of_Augmented_Reality_on_E-Commerce?f_r=5673
- [84]. Karthikeyan (2016), “Problems faced by online customers”, *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 166-169, available at: <http://ijcrme.rdmodernresearch.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/23.pdf>
- [85]. Kaura, V., Durga Prasad, C. S., & Sharma, S. (2015). Service quality, service convenience, price and fairness, customer loyalty, and the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *International journal of bank marketing*, 33(4), 404-422. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277930980_Service_quality_service_convenience_price_and_fairness_customer_loyalty_and_the_mediating_role_of_customer_satisfaction

- [86]. Kaushik, N.A. and Srinivasa, R.P. (2017) 'Effect of website quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intention in online travel ticket booking websites', *Management*, Vol. 7, No. 5, pp.168–173.
- [87]. Khairudin, S. M. H. H. S., & Amin, M. (2019). TOWARDS ECONOMIC GROWTH: THE IMPACT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON PERFORMANCE OF SMES. *Journal of Security & Sustainability Issues*, 9(1).
- [88]. Khalil, N. (2014). Factors affecting the consumer's attitudes on online shopping in Saudi Arabia, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(11), 1-8.
- [89]. Kim, G., & Koo, H (2016). The causal relationship between risk and trust in the onlinemarketplace: A bidirectional perspective. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 55, 1020–1029. 10.1016/j.chb.2015.11.005.
- [90]. Ko, Y. M., Roh, S., & Lee, T. K. (2020). The association of problematic internet shopping with dissociation among South Korean internet users. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(9), 3235. Retrieved July 13, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17093235>
- [91]. Koksai, M.H. (2016) 'The intentions of Lebanese consumers to adopt mobile banking', *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 34, No. 3, pp.327–346.
- [92]. Kotler, A. (2015). *Foundations of Marketing (Custom Edition)*. Melbourne: P.Ed Custom Books.
- [93]. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management. Global Edition (15 Global, Vol. 15E)*. England: Pearson Education Limited. Retrieved April 31, 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911760903022556>
- [94]. Kumar, M., & Velmurugan, R. (2017). Customer satisfaction towards online shopping in Coimbatore district. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, (15), 41–49. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321491597_Customer_Satisfaction_Towards_Online_Shopping_in_Coimbatore_District on 21/3/2019
- [95]. Kumar, Mathan & Velmurugan, Ramaswamy. (2017). Customer Satisfaction Towards Online Shopping in Coimbatore District. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*. 117. 41-49.
- [96]. Kumar, S., & Mohan, K. L. C. (2018). A study on customer satisfaction towards online shopping concerning Namakkal District. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education*, 3(1), 349-350.
- [97]. Kurniawan, E. (2016). Faktor Harga, Persepsi Kualitas Produk dan Pelayanan Terhadap Minat Untuk Membeli Keramik Merek Platinum Pada PD Setia Jaya di Pontianak. *Bisma*, 1(6), 1287–1299.
- [98]. Liang, L. J., Choi, H. C., & Joppe, M. (2018). Exploring the relationship between satisfaction, trust and switching intention, repurchase intention in the context of Airbnb. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 69, 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2017.10.015> [Crossref], [Web of Science®], [Google Scholar]
- [99]. Libo-on, J, T. (2021). Service quality influence customer satisfaction in courier services: A comparative study. *International Journal of Business Management (AIJBM)*, 4(3), 51-63.
- [100]. Ludin, I. H. B. H., & Cheng, B. L. (2014). Factors influencing customer satisfaction and E-Loyalty: Online shopping environment among the young adults. *Management Dynamics in the Knowledge Economy*, 2(3), 462–471. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/157e82f50851b5b2a12eefb5161e7fc/1?pqorigsite=gscholar&cbl=2032295> on 21/7/2019
- [101]. Madrigal, D. &. (2012). Strengths and Weaknesses of Quantitative and Qualitative Research. *UXmatters*.
- [102]. Mahmud, K., Imtiaz, M., & Ahmed, W. U. (2019). General consumer satisfaction towards online shopping in Bangladesh. *Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics and Law*, 18(2), 11-21. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/GENERAL-CONSUMER-SATISFACTION-TOWARDS-ONLINE-IN-Mahmud-Md./18aaf05aa2acdd300bd62f1977fc4413fc99a3e0>
- [103]. Makudza, F., 2021. Augmenting customer loyalty through customer experience management in the banking industry. *Journal of Asian Business and Economic Studies*, 27(2), pp. 191- 203. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABES-01-2020-0007>.
- [104]. Makudza, F., 2021. Augmenting customer loyalty through customer experience management in the banking industry. *Journal of Asian Business and Economic Studies*. 27(2), pp. 191-203. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABES-01-2020-0007>.
- [105]. Mascarenhas J. (2018). Customer Satisfaction in Online Shopping - Retail Industry
- [106]. McBurney, D. & White, T. (2009). *Research Methods*. New York, NY: Cengage Learning.
- [107]. McKnight, D. H., Cummings, L. L., & Chervany, N. L. (2002). Trust formation in new organizational relationships. *Academy of Management Review*, 23(3), 473-490.
- [108]. Mehrotra, A., Elias, H., Al-Alawi, A.I., & Al-Bassam, S.A. (2020). The effect of demographic factors of consumers online shopping behavior in a GCC university. In E.A, Al-A'ali, & M, Masmoudi (Eds). *Ethical Consumerism and Comparative Studies Hossain et al., International Journal of Business Ecosystem & Strategy*. 4(3) (2022) 13-22. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335821695_The_Effect_of_Demographic_Factors_of_Consumers_Online_Shopping_Behavior_in_a_GCC_University

- [109]. Merbitz, C. T., Merbitz, N. H., & Pennypacker, H. S. (2016). On terms: Frequency and rate in applied behavior analysis. *The Behavior Analyst*, 39, 333-338.
- [110]. Mikulic, J., Krešić, D., and Šerić, M. (2021). The factor structure of medical tourist satisfaction: exploring key drivers of choice, delight, and frustration. *J. Hospital. Tour. Res.* 1177:1096348020987273. doi: 10.1177/1096348020987273
- [111]. Mofokeng, T. E. (2021). The impact of online shopping attributes on customer satisfaction and loyalty: Moderating effects of e-commerce experience. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1968206. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354328490_The_impact_of_online_shopping_attributes_on_customer_satisfaction_and_loyalty_Moderating_effects_of_e-commerce_experience
- [112]. Mohamed, R. N., Rusli, M. S., & Borhan, H. (2021). Modelling the effectiveness of using online food delivery services apps among customers in Klang valley during Covid-19 pandemics/Prof Madya. Dr Rozita Naina Mohamed...[et al.].
- [113]. Mohammed, A. (2014). Determinants of young consumers' online shopping intention. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 6(1), pp.475-482.
- [114]. Morales, D., Alejandro, A. C., & Esteban-Millat, I. (2023). The effect of flow experience in the adoption of online supermarkets applying the technology acceptance model (TAM). [El efecto de la experiencia de flujo en la adopción de los supermercados en línea aplicando el modelo de aceptación de tecnología (TAM)] *Questiones Publicitarias*, 6(32), 41-54. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/qp.387>
- [115]. Mortimer, G., Fazal e Hasan, S., Andrews, L., & Martin, J. (2016). Online grocery shopping: The impact of shopping frequency on perceived risk. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 26, 202–223. 10.1080/09593969.2015.1130737.
- [116]. Mortimer, G., Neale, L., Hasan, S.F.E. and Dunphy, B. (2015) 'Investigating the factors influencing the adoption of m-banking: a cross cultural study', *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 33, No. 4, pp.545–570.
- [117]. Müller, A., De Zwaan, M., Mitchell, J. E., & Zimmermann, T. (2016). Pathological buying and partnership status. *Psychiatry Research*, 239, 122–123. Retrieved July 13, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2016.03.013>
- [118]. Murfield, M., Boone, C. A., Rutner, P., & Thomas, R. (2017). Investigating logistics service quality in omnichannel retailing. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 47(4), 263-296. DOI: 10.1108/IJPDLM-06-2016-0161
- [119]. Musa, A., Khan, H. U., & AlShare, K. A. (2015). Factors influence consumers' adoption of mobile payment devices in Qatar. *International journal of mobile communications*, 13(6), 670-689.
- [120]. Musa, H., Ab Rahim, N., Azmi, F. R., Shibghatullah, A. S., & Othman, N. A. (2016). Social media marketing and online small and medium enterprises performance: Perspective of Malaysian small and medium enterprises. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(7), 1-5.
- [121]. Nepomuceno, M. V., Laroche, M., & Richard, M. O. (2014). How to reduce perceived risk when buying online: The interactions between intangibility, product knowledge, brand familiarity, privacy and security concerns. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(4), 619-629.
- [122]. Ok, S., Suy, R., Chhay, L., & Choun, C. (2018). Customer Satisfaction and Service Quality in the Marketing Practice: Study on Literature Review. *Asian Themes in Social Sciences Research*, 1(1), 2018th ser., 21-27. doi:10.33094/journal.139.2018.11.21.27
- [123]. Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533-544. doi: 10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y
- [124]. Pandey, A. and Parmar, J. (2019) 'Factors affecting consumer's online shopping buying behavior', in *Proceedings of 10th International Conference on Digital Strategies for Organizational Success*.
- [125]. Pandey, N., Tripathi, A., Jain, D., and Roy, S. (2020). Does price tolerance depend upon the type of product in e-retailing? role of customer satisfaction, trust, loyalty, and perceived value. *J. Strateg. Market.* 28, 522–541. doi: 10.1080/0965254X.2019.1569109
- [126]. Patel, D. S. (2015). Evolution of Online shopping in India & its Unparallel Growth. *International Journal for Research in Management and Pharmacy*, 4(3), 2320- 0901.
- [127]. Perera, G. A. B. S., & Sachitra, K. M. V. (2019). Customer satisfaction towards online shopping in Sri Lanka: Moderating effect of income level. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 1-10.
- [128]. Prasetyo, Y. T., & Fuente, D. G. D. D. (2020, September). Determinant factors affecting customer satisfaction among Filipinos in Lazada online shopping during COVID-19 pandemic: A structural equation modeling approach. In *2020 7th International Conference on Frontiers of Industrial Engineering (ICFIE)* (pp. 48-52). IEEE. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347334183_Determinant_Factors_Affecting_Customer_Satisfaction_among_Filipinos_in_Lazada_Online_Shopping_during_COVID-19_Pandemic_A_Structural_Equation_Modeling_Approach
- [129]. Puji Lestari, F. A. (2018). Pengaruh Web E-Commerce, Kualitas Produk dan 56 Kualitas Layanan terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen. *Sosio E-Kons*, 10(1), 87. Retrived April 29, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.30998/sosioekons.v10i1.2411>

- [130]. Rahi, S. (2017). Research design and methods: A systematic review of research paradigms, sampling issues and instruments development. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 6(2), 1-5. DOI: 10.4172/2162-6359.1000403
- [131]. Rahmawati, Tiwow, C., & Ramadhan, G. (2020). Pengaruh Produk dan Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Jung Coffee Rawamangun. *Ekbang*, 3(1), 1–6.
- [132]. Rajah, R. K. (2018). Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping (Doctoral dissertation, Multimedia University).
- [133]. Raman, P. (2019). Understanding female consumers' intention to shop online: The role of trust, convenience and customer service. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 31(4), 1138–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-10-2018-0396>
- [134]. Razar, I. (2016). The impact of product quality and price on customer satisfaction with the mediator of customer Value. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, vol.30.
- [135]. RetailDive.com (2016, May 10). Quality product content prevents online shopping cart abandonment. Retrieved online from <https://www.retaildive.com/news/quality-product-content-prevents-online-shopping-cart-abandonment/418638/>
- [136]. Rita, P., Oliveira, T., & Farisa, A. (2019). the impact of e-service quality and customer satisfaction on customer behavior in online shopping. *Heliyon*, 5(10), e02690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02690>
- [137]. Romdonny, J., and Rosmadi, M.L.N. (2019). Factors Affecting Customer Loyalty in Products. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal Vol 2 (1): 337-343*.
- [138]. Rudansky-kloppers, S. (2014). Investigating factors influencing customer online buying satisfaction in Gauteng, South Africa. *International Business & Economics Research Journal*, 13(5), 1187–1198. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Sharon_RudanskyKloppers/publication/297750316_Investigating_Factors_Influencing_Customer_Online_Buying_Satisfaction_In_Gauteng_South_Africa/links/5829c28c08ae911e2a3272f9/Investigating-Factors-Influencing-Customer-Online-Buying-Satisfaction-In-Gauteng-South-Africa.pdf on 17/3/2019
- [139]. Rungsiswat, S., Sriyakul, T., Jernsittiparsert, K. (2019). The era of e-commerce & online marketing risks associated with online shopping. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and change*. 8(8), 201-221.
- [140]. Sam, C. Y., and Sharma, C., 2015. An exploration into the factors driving consumers in Singapore towards or away from the adoption of online shopping. *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal*. 7(1), pp. 60-73.
- [141]. Sambargi, S., & Gopal, R. (2016). Predicting online buying using shopping orientation - A study on online grocery shopping among women. *PES Business Review*, 11(1), 35. doi: 10.21842/pes/2016/v11/i1/108930
- [142]. Santos, K. E. S., & Santos, A. R. (2020). Factors Affecting Consumer Satisfaction to Online Shopping. *International Journal of Humanities and Education Development (IJHED)*, 2(6), 571-575.
- [143]. Saripah, S., Putri, A. A., dan Darwin, R. (2016). Pengaruh Kepercayaan, Persepsi Kebermanfaatan, Persepsi Risiko dan Kepuasan Wajib Pajak Terhadap Penggunaan efilling bagi Wajib Pajak Orang Pribadi di KPP Pratama Pekanbaru Tampan Tahun 2015. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Ekonomika*, 6(2), 134-149.
- [144]. Shalini, G.R., & Malini, K.S.H. (2015). A study of online shopping website characteristics and its impact on consumer intention to purchase online in Chennai, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2(9), 412-418. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.academia.edu/34972204/A_STUDY_OF_ONLINE_SHOPPING_WEBSITE_CHARACTERISTICS_AND_ITS_IMPACT_ON_CONSUMER_INTENTION_TO_PURCHASE_ONLINE_IN_CHENNAI
- [145]. Sharip, Z., Abd. Razak, S. B., Noordin, N., & Yusoff, F. M. (2020). Application of an effective microorganism product as a cyanobacterial control and water quality improvement measure in Putrajaya Lake, Malaysia. *Earth Systems and Environment*, 4(1), 213-223.
- [146]. Sharma, A., Sharma, A., & Kaur, H. (2020). Comparative Analysis Between Online and Offline Shopping Approach and Behavior of Consumers. *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience*, 17(11), 4965-4970. Retrieved from: <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/contentone/asp/jctn/2020/00000017/00000011/art00029>
- [147]. Sharma, B.K., & Parmar, S. (2018). Impact of demographic factors on online purchase intention through social media- With reference to Pune, Maharashtra. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*. 5(1), 45-50. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325360961_IMPACT_OF_DEMOGRAPHIC_FACTORS_ON_ONLINE_PURCHASE_INTENTION_THROUGH_SOCIAL_MEDIA-WITH_REFERENCE_TO_PUNE_MAHARASHTRA
- [148]. Sharma, H., & Aggarwal, A. G. (2019). Finding determinants of e-commerce success: A PLS-SEM approach. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 16(4), 453–471. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAMR-08-2018-0074>

- [149]. Shin, J. I., Chung, K. H., Oh, J. S., & Lee, C. W. (2013). The effect of site quality on repurchase intention in Internet shopping through mediating variables: The case of university students in South Korea. *International Journal of Information Management*, 33, 453–463. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2013.02.003>
- [150]. Shohel, M. (2013). Investigation of consumer attitudes, intentions and brand loyal behavior on the OTC drugs in Bangladesh. *British Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 3(3), 454-464. doi: 10.9734/bjpr/2013/3717
- [151]. Shumba, T., and Ferreira, D. (2023). Quality expectation factors influencing e-customer satisfaction: evidence from online shopping in South Africa. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(2), 2023, 75-94 DOI: 10.15604/ejss.2023.11.02.004
- [152]. Simanjuntak, M., Putri, N. E., Yuliati, L. N., & Sabri, M. F. (2020). Enhancing customer retention using customer relationship management approach in the car loan business. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1). doi:10.1080/23311975.2020.1738200
- [153]. Singh, N (2018). "Online apparel shopping," *Man-Made Textiles in India*, vol. 46, retrieved April 31, 2023, from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353194157>.
- [154]. Singh, P., Kashyap, R. (2015). Online shopping behavior of consumers. Jaipur: *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*. Retrieved November 15, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346312030_Online_Shopping_Behaviour_of_Consumers
- [155]. Sopadjieva, E., Dholakia, U., & Benjamin, B. (2017). A study of 46,000 shoppers shows that omnichannel retailing works. *Harvard Business Review*, 3.
- [156]. Souca, M.L., (2014). Customer dissatisfaction and delight: completely different concepts, or part of a satisfaction continuum? *Management & Marketing*, 9(1).
- [157]. Sramova, B., & Pavelka, J. (2019). Gender differences and wellbeing values in adolescent online shopping. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 47(6), 623-642.
- [158]. Suhendar, U., & Ruswanti, E. (2019). Effect of Product Quality, Perception of Price and Satisfaction
- [159]. Sunitha & Gnanadhas, Edwin. (2014). Online Shopping - An Overview. *B-DIGEST*. 6. 16-22.
- [160]. Susanti, D. (2017). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk Terhadap Minat Konsumen Dalam Membeli Produk Tupperware Pada Perumahan Griya Tika Utama Pekanbaru. *Menara Ekonomi*, 3(5), 23–32.
- [161]. Tahar, A., Riyadh, H. A., Sofyani, H., dan Purnomo, W. E. (2020). Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Security and Intention to Use E-Filing: The Role of Technology Readiness. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 7(9), 537-547.
- [162]. Tandon, U. (2021). Predictors of online shopping in India: an empirical investigation. *J. Market. Anal.* 9, 65–79. doi: 10.1057/s41270-020-00084-6
- [163]. Thangavel, Shenbhagavadivu. (2015). A Study on customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping.
- [164]. Thomas, L. (2020). An introduction to simple random sampling. Retrieved May 31, 2023, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/simple-random-sampling/>
- [165]. Tiruwa, A., Yadav, R., & Suri, P. K. (2018). Moderating effects of age, income and internet usage on Online Brand Community (OBC)-induced purchase intention. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAMR-04-2017-0043>
- [166]. Tiruwa, A., Yadav, R., & Suri, P. K. (2018). Moderating effects of age, income and internet usage on Online Brand Community (OBC)-induced purchase intention. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 15(3), 367-392.
- [167]. Tran, V.D., and Vu, Q. H., 2019. Inspecting the relationship among e-service quality, e-trust, ecustomer satisfaction and behavioral intentions of online shopping customers. *Global Business & Finance Review*, 24(3), pp. 29-42. <https://doi.org/10.17549/gbfr.2019.24.3.29>.
- [168]. Tu, Y.T, Li, M.L, and Chih, H. (2013). An empirical study of corporate brand image, customer perceived value and satisfaction on loyalty in shoes industry. *Journal of Economic and Behavioral studies*, 5(7), 469-483.
- [169]. Tuncer, I., Unusan, C., & Cobanoglu, C. (2020). Service quality, perceived value and customer satisfaction on behavioral intention in restaurants: An integrated structural model. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 22(4), 1–29.
- [170]. Turner, J. (2023). The Main ways Technology Impacts Your Daily Life retrieved April 31, 2023, from <https://tech.co/spn/main-ways-technology-impacts-daily-life>.
- [171]. Tzeng, S., Ertz, M., Jo, M. J., & Sarigollu, E. (2020). Factors affecting customer satisfaction on online shopping holiday. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 39(4).
- [172]. Ulum, F., & Muchtar, R. (2018). Pengaruh E-Service Quality Terhadap E-Customer Satisfaction Website Startup Kaosyay. *Jurnal TEKNO KOMPAK*, Vol. 12, No. 2, 2018, 68-72.
- [173]. Uzun, H., & Poturak, M. (2014). Factors affecting online shopping behavior of consumers. *European Journal of Social and Human Sciences*, 3(3), 163–170. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mersid_Poturak/publication/265905664_Factors_Affecting_Online_Shopping_Behavior_of_Consumers/links/542038760cf203f155c2ce2e.pdf on 21/5/2019
- [174]. Vadivu T.S. (2015). A Study on consumer satisfaction towards online shopping. *Sumedha Journal of Management*, vol.4, No.2, pp:4-28.
- [175]. Vaidya, Alpana. (2017). Online shopping trends among college students. *International Journal of English language literature in humanities*.

- [176]. Vasić N., Kilibarda, M., & Kaurin T., (2018). The Influence of Online Shopping Determinants on Customer Satisfaction in the Serbian Market
- [177]. Vasić, N., Kilibarda, M., and Kaurin, T., 2019. The influence of online shopping determinants on customer satisfaction in the Serbian market. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 14(2), pp. 70-89. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4067/S0718-18762019000200107>.
- [178]. Veerajay, Dr. B. (2019). Customers' satisfaction towards online shopping with special reference to Vijayawada City. *Journal of Business and Management*, 21(3), 40-44.
- [179]. Vijay, S., Prashar, S., and Sahay, V., 2019. The influence of online shopping values and web atmospheric cues on e-loyalty: Mediating role of e-satisfaction. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 14(1), pp. 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-18762019000100102>.
- [180]. Visser, J.; Nemoto, T.; Browne, M. Home Delivery and the Impacts on Urban Freight Transport: A Review. *Procedia-Soc. Behav. Sci.* 2014, 125, 15–27.
- [181]. Wahyuni, S. & Ginting, M. (2017). The impact of product quality, price and distribution on purchasing decision on the Astra motor products in Jakarta. *Arthatama: Journal of Business Management and Accounting*, 1(1), 18.
- [182]. Wahyuni, S. & Ginting, M. (2017). The impact of product quality, price and distribution on purchasing decision on the Astra motor products in Jakarta. *Arthatama: Journal of Business Management and Accounting*, 1(1), 18.
- [183]. Wantara, P., & Tambrin, M. (2019). The Effect of price and product quality towards customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on madura batik. *International Tourism and Hospitality Journal*, 2(1), 1-9.
- [184]. Wen, T. S., Mohd Satar N. M., Ishak N. A., & Ating R., (2020). Consumer's acceptance of online shopping in Malaysia. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance, and Business*, 5(27), 93 - 117.
- [185]. Wulan, E. R., & Husaeni, U. A. (2015). Analysis of the variables that affect bookstore customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Nusantara Islam*, 3(2), 27-36.
- [186]. Yeo, V. C. S., Goh, S. K., & Rezaei, S. (2017). Consumer experiences, attitude and behavioral intention toward online food delivery (OFD) services, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 35, 150-162.
- [187]. Yildiz, E. (2017). Effects of service quality on customer satisfaction, trust, customer loyalty and word of mouth: an application on cargo companies in gümüşhane. *Global Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, 6(12), 81-88.
- [188]. Zandi GholamReza, Ayesha Aslam, Muhammad Umar Nasir, Yajing Zhang (2018). Smart Phones and Brand Equity: A Study of Malaysian Consumer Buying Behavior. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7 (4.29), 2018.
- [189]. Zendehtdel, M., Paim, L. H., & Osman, S. B. (2015). Students' online purchasing behavior in Malaysia: understanding online shopping attitude, *Cogent Business & Management*, 2(1), 1-13.
- [190]. Zhang, B., & Kim, J. H. (2013). Luxury fashion consumption in China: Factors affecting attitude and purchase intent. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 20(1), 68-79.
- [191]. Zhang, K. Z. K., Cheung, C. M. K., & Lee, M. K. O. (2014). Examining the moderating effect of inconsistent reviews and its gender differences on consumers' online shopping decision. *International Journal of Information Management*, 34(2), 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2013.12.001> dated May 10, 2023
- [192]. Ziaullah, M., Feng, Y., & Akhter, S. N. (2014). E-Loyalty: The influence of product quality and delivery services on e-trust and esatisfaction in China. *International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology*, 3(10), 20–31.
- [193]. Zulkarnain, K., Ismail, Y., Haque, A. A., & Ahmed, S. (2015). Key success factors of online food ordering services: an empirical study, *Malaysian Management Review*, 50(2), 19-36.